

Analysis of School Management in Realizing Quality Culture in Madiun City

Lismawati¹, Rudi handoko², Rachmawati Novaria³

^{1,2}Fakultas Ilmu Sosial dan Ilmu Politik, Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Surabaya

lismaninda@gmail.com¹, rudi@untag-sby.ac.id², nova@untag-sby.ac.id³

Abstract

The implementation of the school management system has a strategic role in supporting the implementation of public services at the education unit level. The role and function of supervision are needed to monitor, foster, assess, and provide professional guidance to principals, teachers, and education personnel in their target schools. The phenomenon in the field shows a gap in the quality standards of education set by the government and its implementation. No school has met the SNP of the 71 primary schools in Madiun City. This research was conducted because elementary schools in Madiun City do not yet have a quality culture according to the standards set by the government. This study aims to: a. Describe and analyze school management in realizing a quality culture. b. Analyze the factors inhibiting and supporting school management in realizing a quality culture. c. Develop a management model that can encourage a quality culture. The study was conducted qualitatively. The results of the study are as follows; a. The management of elementary schools in Madiun City has met the criteria for quality culture, but at the implementation level, it is not optimal. It can be seen that school management is not optimal, so the quality culture has not been realized as expected by the government. b. Supporting factors, schools are committed to implementing SPMI towards quality cultured schools following applicable regulations, supported by educators and education staff who have the appropriate qualifications. Provisions, a management information system, and the availability of special officers. The inhibiting factor is the low achievement value of implementing curriculum aspects that do not follow the provisions because of the application of local content curriculum aspects. The regulation of learning load based on the form of material deepening is still low, and the implementation of the learning and assessment process is not following the provisions. c. school management model to make school management more effective requires maximum stakeholder involvement through the Development of All Schools.

Keywords: School Management, Quality Culture, Elementary School

A. Introduction

According to the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 25 of 2009 concerning Public Services that the government is obliged to provide quality public services. Standard public service is needed to achieve quality public service. The implementation of the school management system has a strategic role in supporting the implementation of public services in the field of education at the education unit level. In order to improve the quality of the school

as a whole, a unique approach is needed so that all components of the school together have a quality culture.

School management is needed to ensure that education management is carried out with quality standards under government policies. The quality of primary and secondary education in question is the level of conformity between primary and secondary education implementation with the National Education Standards (SNP) in schools. The quality of education in schools tends not to improve without being accompanied by a quality culture.

The quality culture of primary education is essentially a unity of elements consisting of integrated organizations, policies, and processes that regulate all activities to improve quality systematically, planned, and sustainably. Quality culture aims to ensure the fulfillment of standards in education units in a systemic, holistic, and sustainable manner. So quality assurance is needed that spurs the growth and development of a quality culture in the education unit independently and functions as a controller of the implementation of education by the education unit in realizing quality education.

On the other hand, as one of the critical pillars in improving the quality of education in the education unit, the school superintendent has the function, duty, and responsibility to participate in realizing quality education actively. Based on the Permenpan and RB RI Number 14 of 2016, which is an amendment to the Permenpan and RB RI Number 21 of 2010, one of the primary duties of school supervisors is to monitor the implementation of national education standards.

The phenomenon in the field is that the quality standards of education set by the government are different from those implemented by schools. So that most of the quality produced has not met the expected standards, and the quality of educational results has not been commensurate with the desired quality, so the market does not absorb graduates. The weak managerial competence of education managers in education units impacts the quality of education services that have not been standardized.

Schools as formal educational institutions should be managed professionally, so it is necessary to use modern educational management theories. Modern management theory considers that the organization as an open system, based on conceptual analysis and empirical data, is systemically and integratively. The school's commitment to realizing a quality school is an absolute requirement in carrying out comprehensive, continuous, and forward-oriented school development. The achievement of quality culture is indicated by the quality report card, which reflects the achievement of 8 (eight) National Education Standards.

Out of 71 elementary schools in Madiun City, no school has met the SNP. However, on the other hand, public services in education, which are part of the quality culture, have had proud results. In 2016, it became the first national-level rank in public service through the DOPARI SAKATU program (Fairy Tales on Tuesdays, Thursdays, and Saturdays). Even as a follow-up, a Mayor Regulation (Perwali) was made regarding the obligation to implement DOPARI SAKATU for all schools in Madiun City.

Data on quality achievements support the non-achievement of SNP. It can be informed that the quality achievements in 2016 are: Graduate Competency Standard 5.98 towards SNP 4; The Content Standard reached 5.31 towards SNP 4; Process Standard 5.66 towards SNP 4; Assessment Standard 5.04 towards SNP 4; Standards of Educators and Education Personnel 4.05 towards SNP 3; Sarpras standard 5.17 towards SNP 4; Management Standard 5.46, towards SNP 4; Financing Standard 4.37 towards SNP 3. The achievement of the quality of education in 2016 shows that no school has met the SNP.

The quality achievements in 2017 are: Graduate Competency Standards 6.11 towards SNP 4; The Content Standard reached 5.81 towards SNP 4; Process Standard 6.60 towards SNP 4; Assessment Standard 6.17 towards SNP 4; Standards of Educators and Education Personnel 4.54 towards SNP 3; Sarpras standard 4.26 towards SNP 3; Management Standard 6.01, towards SNP 4; Financing Standard 5.71 towards SNP 4. This data shows that in 2017 no school reached the SNP. The quality achievements in 2018 are Graduate Competency Standard 6.39 towards SNP 4; The Content Standard reached 6.17 towards SNP 4; Process Standard 6.69 towards SNP; Assessment Standard 6.44 towards SNP 4; Standards of Educators and Education Personnel 4.37 towards SNP 3; Sarpras standard 4.19 towards SNP 3; Management Standard 6.23, towards SNP 4; Financing Standard 5.90 towards SNP 4. The quality achievements in 2018 show that no school has reached SNP. Based on this data, it is indicated that elementary schools in Madiun City do not yet have a quality culture according to the standards set by the government.

The realization of a quality culture at the elementary school level in Madiun City is interesting to study. It is suspected to be able to provide the color of education in Madiun City. This research focuses on analyzing school management in realizing a quality culture.

Based on the description of the data presented in both theoretical aspects and empirical phenomena, it is considered necessary to analyze school management to realize quality culture, supporting factors, and obstacles and find a quality management model that can encourage quality culture.

The concept of New Public Service (NPS), as introduced by Janet V. Denhardt and Robert B. Denhardt, brings a new paradigm of public service, namely public service, that pays attention to and focuses on the interests of citizens. Provision of services that are more responsive to service users. The needs and interests of service users should be the primary considerations in the overall process of providing public services. Schools, as public institutions, should provide excellent service by providing quality education. To realize quality requires quality management through the application of school-based management. School-based Management.

School-based management is an idea that places the authority of school management in a whole system entity. According to Finn, effective school and school-based management can be observed as follows: "The improvements in student achievement are most likely to be gained their problem and in which strong leadership, particularly by the principal, is a characteristic."

To build an overview of effective school and school-based management, Brown mentioned several elements of the characteristics that must be possessed: (1) autonomy, flexibility, and responsiveness; (2) planning by the principal and school community; (3) adduction of neurons by the principal; (4) a participatoring school environment; (5) collaboration and collegiality among staff; and (6) a heightened sense of personal efficacy for principals and teacher.

School-based management is also a concept that offers autonomy to schools to improve the quality, efficiency, and equity of education to accommodate the local community's interests and establish close cooperation between schools, communities, and the government. School-based management provides broad opportunities for principals, teachers, and students to innovate and improvise in schools related to curriculum, learning, managerial and other issues.

Implementing school-based management requires a healthy process to develop professional skills and culture. Therefore, it is necessary to know the components of the "school-based", Namely management, learning process, human resources, and resources and administration.

If school-based education management in Indonesia can be seen as a new concept and paradigm in its implementation, it must start in various stages. Because it is a new paradigm, its implementation certainly needs to pay attention to the possibilities for schools to be willing to adopt it. Thus, the implementation of school-based management can be categorized as a process of educational innovation, where the success of its implementation is still largely determined by various factors.

In the new paradigm of education management, a principal must at least be able to function as an educator, manager, administrator, supervisor, leader, innovator, motivator, figure, and mediator. The concept of school-based management has become part of government policy. Therefore, Thomas L. Wheeler argues that achieving practical change goals requires clarity of objectives, both those concerning processes and developments by involving internal and external aspects to be taken into consideration. Individuals, principals, teachers, employees, and the condition of the school itself are dotted with goals, mastery of skills, attitudes, self concept, habits of results, and processes. Agents of change are teachers and principals, while the objects of change are institutions, curriculum, learning, et cetera.

School-based management embodied in developing school independence demands the creation of a new institutional order and culture. School-based management is intended to include: (1) the establishment of a school headmaster board that serves as a forum to accommodate the aspirations and needs of school stakeholders, as well as a body that functions to help schools to abandon their performance for the realization of quality educational services and learning outcomes; (2) development of school strategic planning that describes the direction of school development in the perspective of the next 3-4 years. This planning is formulated the vision and mission of the school, analysis of the school's institutional position (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges), the study of strategic issues faced, formulation of school priority programs, formulation of school development goals, achievement of goals, control, and evaluation of the achievement of development goals. School strategy planning is carried out with the school committee; (3) the development of an annual school plan that describes the operational activities of the school accompanied by the planning of the school financing budget. The school's annual planning is drawn up with the school committee; (4) conduct internal monitoring and self-assessment, which is carried out regularly, and report the results in the school committee forum. What aspects are of concern, what the format or instruments are, and who or how task forces do so need to be discussed further. The results of this internal monitoring and self-assessment are significant as material to find out the progress of the school, the results of achievements achieved, and what obstacles and serious problems the school faces; and (5) to report an annual report describing the implementation of the school's annual planning.

Quality Culture. According to the Ministry of National Education (2010), school quality culture is defined as the entire system of thinking, values, morals, norms, and human beliefs. Human life continues to develop, so what develops is the social system, the economic

system, the belief system, science, technology, and art. Education is a planned effort to develop students' potential to have a system of thinking, values, morals, and beliefs inherited by their society and develop that legacy in a direction appropriate for present and future life. According to Husaini Usman (2006: 407), quality is the suitability of market needs and how far a product has met the requirements that have been set. It was further explained that the quality aspects include: (1) excellent service to customers, high social responsibility, and customer satisfaction; (2) the customer is numbered together, and the learner is the center of attention.

Quality in education includes inputs, processes, outputs, and outcomes. Input is declared quality if it is ready for processing. The quality education process can create an atmosphere of Innovative Active Learning Kreatif, Effective and Fun. Output is declared quality if the student's academic and non-academic learning outcomes are high. Outcomes are declared quality if graduates are absorbed in the world of work. Quality characteristics include (1) good teacher performance; (2) be punctual; (3) long-lasting excellent service; (4) the school has good endurance; (5) beautiful and attractive schools; (6) school residents have moral values and professionalism; (7) facilities and infrastructure are available and easy to use; (8) the school has an SPM; (9) consistency; (10) able to serve. In TQM, philosophically, the concept of quality emphasizes the constant search for continuous improvement to achieve customer needs and satisfaction. Some of these opinions can be concluded that the school quality culture is the entire thinking system, values, morals, norms, beliefs (belief), thinking systems, values, morals norms which are substantial for excellent service to customers (students).

Improving the quality of education depends on the paradigm used in developing schools and the commitment of each component of education to carry out quality education. According to Jerome S. Arcaro (2007:10-11), quality schools begin with formulating and developing a vision and mission. The quality vision and mission focus on the community's total needs in the program, developing a system of measuring the value of education, supporting the critical systems, staff, and students to manage change and continuous improvement by always striving to make educational products better. This process is established in five quality education options: focus on customers, total engagement, measurement, commitment, and continuous improvement (Arcaro, 2007: 12-13).

Diagram 1. Pillars of the School of Total Quality (Arcaro, 2007: 15)

These five pillars are considered a strong foundation for managing the education and quality variables.

The challenge of continuous quality improvement is a quickly satisfied attitude towards something that has been achieved. Educational professionals do not know the comfort zone to improve the quality of education. The intended comfort zone is that people do not want to be creative anymore to achieve higher achievements (Chatib, 2011: 13). Mt. Edgecumbe High School in Alaska, as a model school, has implemented 15 principles of TQM (Total Quality Management) that are considered suitable to be modeled or a model of education management in the country. The fifteen principles are (1) maintain goals towards the advancement of learners and the continuous improvement of services; (2) apply the latest philosophy; (3) strive to eliminate the ratings and harmful effects of human classifications; (4) stop relying on exams to achieve quality; (5) cooperate with educational institutions where learners come from; (6) continuously develop a student engagement system and service system to improve quality and productivity; (7) conduct education and job training for learners, teachers, staff and administrators; (8) build leadership; (9) eliminate fear; (10) break down barriers between departments/programs; (11) eliminate slogans, demands and targets for teachers and learners in order to achieve perfect performance and productivity levels; (12) eliminate targets for teachers and learners, for example a 10% increase in test scores and a 15% reduction in dropout rates, replacing them with leadership targets; (13) eliminate obstacles that can undermine the pride and work of teachers, students and management; (14) organize quality education and self-development programs for everyone; and (15) involve everyone in the school in an effort to make a transformation (Dryden and Vos, 1999: 408).

The mindset of the education reform movement is oriented towards a quality culture. The macro context of quality culture begins with political decisions, regulatory formulation, and policies. Furthermore, in the micro context, the quality of education begins with

formulating the vision and mission of the institution, management, and participation. Formulating the institution's vision, mission, and management policies lead to school quality behavior. In that context, Iryanto (2008) offers five ideas of quality and excellence that should be possessed by all components of the school, especially educational executors, such as school leaders, teachers, students, and parents of students. The five ideas he intended were to think and act to produce the best, be oriented to the future, be open and adaptive to change, make continuous improvements, and change the way things are viewed.

The secretary's commission on achieving necessary skills in the United States, as cited by Dryden and Vos (1999: 276), found three keys to a quality school future: (1) a well-developed mind; (2) high passion for learning; and (3) the ability to combine knowledge with work (a well-developed mind, a passion for learning, and the ability to put knowledge to work).

According to Sutarto (2015: 115), the ability to adapt to changes or even become an agent of change is the key to success. Mt. Edgecumbe-Alaska High School is a model school that Gordon Dryden and Jeannette Vos exemplify as a school that consistently maintains quality amid changing times. The school maintains quality because it carries out modern educational management by basing itself on the following twelve beliefs (Dryden and Vos, 1999: 406): (1) human relations are the foundation for all quality development; (2) all components in our organization can be continuously improved; (3) solving the source of the problem inside the system will inevitably lead to the improvement of the system; (4) the person who performs a job is the one who knows the most about the work; (5) everyone wants to be involved and wants to do their job well; (6) everyone wants their role to be appreciated; (7) working in a team is more able to develop the system than working individually; (8) a problem-solving process structured with problem-solving techniques through statistical graphs allows you to know your position, where the variations are, the priority of the problem to be solved, and whether the changes made have the desired influence; (9) unhealthy relationships are unproductive and outdated; (10) each organization has hidden gems that must be unearthed and found; (11) removing barriers to work pride and learning is the valid key to unlocking the potential of organizations that have not been touched so far; (12) continuous training, learning and experimentation are the key to sustainable growth.

Furthermore, Dryden and Vos (1999: 433,452, 456) mention twelve steps towards a superior school system: (1) plan schools as lifelong centers of community resources; (2) ask your customers, especially students and their parents; (3) guarantee customer success and satisfaction; (4) serve all kinds of intelligence and learning styles of learners; (5) use the best

teaching method; (6) invest in your primary source, the teacher as a facilitator; (7) be all teachers and students at the same time; (8) plan a four-part curriculum (personal growth curriculum, life skills curriculum, learning to learn and learning to think curriculum, content curriculum); (9) change the grading system (50% self-assessment, 30% friend assessment, 20% teacher/supervisor assessment); (10) use future technologies; (11) utilize community members as resources; and (12) give everyone the right to vote.

The Quality Assurance System for Primary and Secondary Education has two main objectives in its implementation. The first objective of the Primary and Secondary Education Quality Assurance System is to control the education organized by the education units in primary and secondary education so that quality education is realized. Second, the Quality Assurance System for Primary and Secondary Education aims to provide guarantees for the fulfillment of standards in academic units systematically, holistically, and sustainably to grow and develop a quality culture in education units independently. The objectives of the second Primary and Secondary Education Quality Assurance System reflect the expectations for the implementation and development of a quality culture in the educational environment.

The success of the best achievements in the implementation of SPMI is inseparable from the cooperation of all school residents, so a robust internal commitment is needed to implement SPMI on an ongoing basis to realize the desired school Quality Culture. For schools to realize a quality culture, it is necessary to build a school commitment to running SPMI according to its cycle. The SPMI cycle is described as follows:

Source : <https://www.mediaeducations.com/2021/08/dokumen- spmi-sistem- penjaminn-mutu.html>

The SPMI cycle consists of (1) Quality mapping, (2) Preparation of quality fulfillment plans, (3) Implementation of quality fulfillment, and (4) Evaluation/quality audit. The cycle must be orderly and continuous, (5) Quality Determination. Thus, implementing the quality

assurance system aims to improve quality by the SNP and encourages the creation of a quality culture education where all components in schools have a learning spirit and continuously develop themselves under the times.

B. Methods

This research examines school management in realizing a quality culture. It is suspected that there has not been only one school that has realized quality culture for three years. Therefore, researchers need to dive into the experiences of educational actors based on reality so that this study follows an interpretive paradigm with a qualitative approach. The interpretive paradigm focuses on the subjective nature of the social world. The interpretive approach aims to analyze social reality and how it is formed. The researcher must dive into the subjective experiences of the perpetrators in order to understand the specific social environment. Interpretive research does not place objectivity as the most important thing, but to obtain a deep understanding, the subjectivity of the perpetrator must be dug deeper to allow a trade-off between objectivity and the depth of research findings (Efferin et al., 2004).

The data processed in this study are primary data and secondary data. Primary data is data obtained directly in the field through in-depth interviews and observations made by researchers, and secondary data is data that has been officially published and obtained from the media, documentation, and archives from related agencies. Reduction, display, and concluding drawing/verification.

C. Results and Discussion

The Education Quality Map (PMP) at the Madiun City level provides an overview of the quality of Madiun City education. Based on the available data and information, it is expected to be an input for the Madiun City Regional Education Quality Assurance Team (TPMPD) to develop a strategic plan to improve the quality of education in the work area in the following year.

The SNP achievement score is in the range of values between 0 (zero) to 7. In this case, the range of value scores is divided into five categories that describe the achievement category of the National Education Standards (SNP). The SNP achievements obtained by each education unit describe the actual condition of the quality map of primary and secondary education achieved by the education unit. Each national education standard achievement category group lies between the lower and upper threshold. Meanwhile, to find out and interpret the quality achievements of primary and secondary education using the guidelines for interpreting SNP

achievements as discussed in Chapter 6, namely, a score of 0.00 to 2.04 means: M1; a score of 2.05 to 3.70 means: M2; a score of 3.71 to 5.06 means: M3; a score of 5.07 to 6.66 means: M4; a score of 6.67 to 7.00 means: SNP. Graduate Competency Standards (SKL): Low achievement of scores on the student skills dimension (score 6.2), due to low collaborative thinking and acting skills (value 5.94), the availability of various infrastructures according to the provisions is still low (achievement value 1.32) and the implementation of comprehensive, authentic assessments is still not well implemented (achievement value 5.90). Thus, teachers conducting assessments are less than optimal and have not followed the realm that should be measured. Teachers still conduct assessments in the same way on knowledge, attitudes, and skills. Teachers still often use non-homemade instruments. Regarding assessment facilities, teachers can maximize existing facilities in addition to submitting through the school budget. However, the Madiun City Education Office has facilitated each student/teacher with one laptop regarding learning facilities.

Content Standards: The low achievement of the value of implementing curriculum aspects that are not following the provisions (value 4.79) is caused by the implementation of curriculum aspects on local content (achievement value 4.65) and the regulation of learning load based on the form of material deepening is still low (achievement value 4.71), and the implementation of the learning process has not been following the provisions, especially in obtaining evaluations from school principals and school supervisors (achievement value 2.02) so that the competence of graduates achieved students when exploring these subjects are less than optimal. This data shows that the involvement of the curriculum development team is not optimal, and the curriculum developed must be socialized. This is also due to the lack of optimal assistance from the superintendent of schools. Ideally, a school superintendent accompanies ten primary school institutions. Nevertheless, in reality, a school superintendent must accompany 35-36 elementary school institutions, so the duration of assistance per 3-4 hours visit is reduced because they have to share it with other elementary school institutions.

Process Standards: The analysis results show that the low achievement of learning process planning according to the provisions (achievement value 5.15) is caused by the implementation of evaluations from school principals and school supervisors that have not been carried out correctly (achievement score 2.02). The implementation of periodic assessment reporting has not been carried out optimally (achievement value 5.59), so student learning activities are less directed to achieving essential competencies, and the development of RPP lacks a reference. Thus, it can be seen that the supervisor's role is less than optimal in assisting

the target schools and the less than optimal learning and learning process from the school superintendent and principal. Moreover, they were triggered by the heavy workload of teachers because, in addition to teaching, there are still additional tasks in the school innovation team that demand teachers' time, energy, and thinking. Teachers have to divide their time between their primary and additional duties due to the limited number of educators at the Primary School level and the absence of administrative personnel precisely, while in elementary schools, there are only OPS.

Education Assessment Standards: The low achievement of the assessment instrument that adjusts the aspects (the achievement of the value of 6.57) is caused because the use of the attitude aspect assessment instrument has not been implemented optimally (achievement value 5.73), and the implementation of the learning process has not been following the provisions, especially in obtaining evaluations from the principal and school supervisors (achievement value 2.02), so that the assessment instrument cannot be used as a control of the assessment quality standards; The level of achievement of student competencies cannot be appropriately measured, and the learning process is not following the established standards. This is supported by suboptimal supervision from the principal and the assistance of the school superintendent, who is less than optimal in assisting the target school. As discussed earlier, the workload of the superintendent of schools is hefty because the number of Superintendents is not equal to the number of schools that must be fostered, so the superintendent of schools must divide as efficiently as possible in carrying out the duties of mentoring the fostered teachers.

Management Standards: The low achievement of management programs implemented following the provisions (achievement value 6.0) is caused by the implementation of student service activities (achievement value 5.1) and in carrying out student self-development activities is less than optimal (achievement value 5.31), so that the vision, mission, and goals of the school cannot be achieved optimally, the quality improvement of graduates cannot be achieved optimally, the empowerment of school resources is not optimal as well.

Financing Standards: The low achievement of schools managing funds properly (achievement value 5.86) is caused by the school in regulating the allocation of funds derived from the APBD / APBN / foundation / other sources less than optimally (achievement value 5.21) and in increasing the usefulness of educators and education personnel is less than optimal (achievement value 5.96) so that schools cannot carry out educational activities regularly and sustainably optimally according to national education standards; some costs do not get funding allocations. The principal and the school treasurer, who are sometimes involved in OPS,

socialization of financial management issues were followed by the principal and the school treasurer. While there are often changes in the treasurer or OPS, it is suspected that they are service personnel and have to replace administrative duties because there is no administrative personnel in elementary schools. Even teachers also get additional tasks related to administration, in addition to OPS. This happens in elementary schools, and there is limited availability of educational personnel. It was also found that the need for educators was still limited and insufficient to meet the available classes, and schools were forced to find service personnel.

School Management Analysis: the data explored related to school management consists of several indicators, namely: (1) curriculum and learning management; (2) student management; (3) management of educators and education personnel; (4) management of facilities and infrastructure; (5) financing management; (6) school based public relations management; (7) school-based cultural and environmental management.

Curriculum and Learning Management: The low achievement of the value of implementing curriculum aspects that are not following the provisions is due to the implementation of curriculum aspects on local content, and the regulation of learning loads based on the form of deepening the material is still low. Teachers allocate time for structured assignments and unstructured independent activities to students a maximum of 40% of the time allocation for each subject, but those who apply according to the rules are only about 29 schools (40%) out of 71 schools in Madiun City. The school develops the curriculum using the principles of KTSP development, even though the involvement of the school curriculum development team is less than optimal.

The implementation of the learning process has not been following the provisions, especially in getting evaluations from school principals and school supervisors so that the competence of graduates achieved by students when exploring these subjects is not optimal. This shows that if the involvement of the curriculum development team is not optimal, and the curriculum developed must be socialized, this is also due to the lack of optimal assistance from the school supervisor. Ideally, a school superintendent accompanies ten primary school institutions. However, in reality, a school superintendent has to accompany 35-36 primary school institutions. Furthermore, data was obtained that the school has not compiled a syllabus of local content subjects while still using the syllabus made by the Madiun City-level development team.

Student Management: Concerning the results of research on the student management component, it was found that the school carried out student activities which included: (1) data collection of prospective students; (2) admission of new learners (PPDB); (3) school introduction/student orientation; (4) implementation of the learning process; (5) character building of learners; (6) the provision of particular services; (7) supervision, evaluation, and reporting. However, the grouping of students, which is generally not carried out, is not done only incidentally because of a need, such as coaching activities facing competitions.

Management of Educators and Education Personnel: Administrative personnel have minimum academic qualifications in secondary education or equivalent. The school has more administrative personnel than one who has secondary education qualifications or equivalent, has an educational background following their duties, and has more administrative personnel than one whom all have an educational background according to their duties. Minimum library personnel has secondary education academic qualifications or equivalent. The school has more libraries than one that all have secondary education qualifications or equivalent. Library personnel has a letter of assignment as the person in charge of the library.

According to the provisions, OPS in Madiun City has qualifications, 60% linearity, 90% competency fulfillment, and already has an assignment letter. Meanwhile, library personnel of academic quality is met, linearity is 50%, competency fulfillment is 60%, and they already have an assignment letter. The special personnel for academic qualifications is met, the linearity is met, the fulfillment of competencies is 90%, and an assignment letter. This is related to fulfilling the lowest competence and linearity in OPS and library personnel. These two types of staff are all wiyata bakti workers with heavy loads. **Facilities and Infrastructure Management:** The quality of education in educational facilities and infrastructure standards has increased, from 4.19 in 2018 to 5.05 in 2019. The score of 5.05 is in the M3 category. Meanwhile, in 2019-2020 it experienced a decrease, namely from a score of 5.05 in 2019 to 4.78 in 2020. The score of 4.78 is in the M3 category.

Indicators of adequate school capacity: the achievement of the quality of education in the capacity of adequate school capacity has increased, namely from a score of 4.55 in 2018 to 5.21 in 2019. The score of 5.21 is in the M4 category. Meanwhile, in 2019-2020 it experienced a decrease, namely from a score of 5.21 in 2019 down to 4.4 in 2020. The score of 4.4 is in the M3 category.

Indicators of schools having complete and decent learning facilities and infrastructure: the achievement of the quality of education in schools has complete and feasible learning

facilities and infrastructure, namely from a score of 2.72 in 2018 increased to 4.67 in 2019. The score of 4.67 is in the M3 category. Meanwhile, in 2019-2020 it experienced an increase, namely from a score of 4.67 in 2019 to 5.8 in 2020. The score of 5.8 is in the M4 category.

Indicators of schools having complete and decent supporting facilities and infrastructure: the achievement of the quality of education in schools has complete and feasible supporting facilities and infrastructure, namely from a score of 2.79 in 2018 increased to 4.72 in 2019. The score of 4.72 is in the M3 category. Meanwhile, in 2019-2020 it experienced an increase, namely from a score of 4.72 in 2019 to 5.6 in 2020. The score of 5.6 is in the M4 category. Although the availability of facilities has not reached the SNP, there has been an increase in the SNP score due to both improvements and procurement. Especially in learning, the government has facilitated 1 (one) student/teacher 1 (one) laptop, which is carried out to continue developing a quality culture following the current situation.

Financing Management: In general, the school has formulated and set the institution's vision, is easy to understand, and is often socialized. The school has formulated and established the institution's mission, is easy to understand, and is often socialized. The school has formulated and set the goals of the institution. Formulate and set goals; it is easy to understand and often socialized. The school has a medium-term work plan (four-year) and an annual work plan. Have a mediumterm work plan and an annual work plan and have been socialized.

The school has financial management guidelines as a basis for the preparation of RKAS. Have financial management guidelines for the last four years in a row. The school has bookkeeping of operating expenses. Have thorough bookkeeping of operating costs for the last three years. The school makes a financial management accountability report and submits it to the government or foundation. Make a financial management accountability report and submit it to the government or foundation for the last four years.

Based on the findings, it is known that the school formulates its vision, mission, and objectives to compile the RKS does not charge tuition fees and has guidelines for financial management. The school prepares financial reports in a transparent and accountable manner. School-Based Public Relations Management: The school engages the community and builds partnerships with other relevant institutions in education management. Have four or more documents supporting community involvement and building partnerships with other relevant institutions in education management.

School-based public relations management in elementary schools involves various elements: principals, educators, education staff, parents/guardians of students, school

committees, and other stakeholders. In the implementation of education in schools, schools can collaborate with: (1) community leaders; (2) parents of students; (3) civic institutions; (4) local governments; and (5) the business world and the industrial world. Based on the research findings, the school involves community-building partnerships. The lowest achievement of public relations in elementary schools involves education providers, principals, teachers, staff, and school committees. So it can be said that the involvement of public relations in realizing a school quality culture is still low.

School-Based Cultural and Environmental Management: Based on the study's findings, it is known that schools create a conducive environment guided by the principles of sustainability, integrated, consistent implementation, fun coaching, and development of school culture reflected in habituation schools socialize school cultural programs. The school formed the school cultural team. The team compiles, implements, and evaluates school cultural programs. The lowest achievement in school culture management is that the school involves the principal, teachers, OPS, staff, committees, and other stakeholders, and the highest in forming the school culture team. So it can be said that the school has a high commitment to realizing the school culture.

Quality Culture Analysis: The quality culture referred to in this study is a culture of independently carrying out the cycle of the Internal Quality Assurance System (SPMI) to achieve SNP. So that the scope of this quality culture is related to the SPMI cycle. So that the research findings presented in this part include: (1) quality mapping; (2) quality fulfillment planning; (3) implementation of quality fulfillment; (4) internal quality audit; (5) the determination of new qualities.

Quality Mapping: Quality mapping begins with forming a School Quality Assurance Team (TPMPS). The establishment of TPMPS is carried out in order to implement the Internal Quality Assurance System (SPMI). The portrait of TPMPS on the implementation of PMP. TPMPS consists of 2 parts: the school development team and the internal auditor team. This team involves school superintendents, principals, teachers, education staff, and school/community committees. Based on the research findings, all schools have formed TPMPS; it is just that the TPMPS at the elementary school level in Madiun City cannot be adequately empowered because of the many duplicate tasks carried out by team members. Currently, many teams are formed within the school and work partially, thus causing the enormous workload of the school and the process of managing the school to overlap, ineffective and inefficient—the role of TPMPS in the implementation of SPMI following the SPMI cycle. Quality mapping of elementary schools in Madiun City, starting with reviewing SNP, is an essential part of quality mapping. All school residents should read

and review the SNP as the first step in quality assurance. There are two essential things in reviewing the results of the EDS (Quality Report Card), namely, printing a quality report card and analyzing the quality report card. Quality Fulfillment Plan: Schools conduct EDS; this is supported by data from all elements stating 100%, EDS uses a quality report card, from the supervisor 90%, teachers 85%, OPS 70%, school committee 80%, school supervisor 70% and TPMPD 100%, achievement 82.5%. Analysis of quality data from principals 70%, teachers, TPMPD 65%, OPS, school committees 60%, school supervisors 55%, achievements 62.5%. Root cause analysis, from the principal and TPMPD elements 70%, OPS and school superintendents 65%, teachers and school committees 60%, achievement 65%. Develop quality planning from principals and teachers 80%, OPS and school superintendents 70%, TPMPD 75%, committees 60%, achievement 72.5%. The lowest achievement of quality data analysis and root cause analysis is suspected to be less than optimal supervisory assistance because the proportion of the number of school supervisors and teachers is not balanced. The suboptimal assistance of the superintendent makes the school less than optimal in preparing a quality fulfillment plan. This is still found in schools that carry out quality fulfillment planning not based on the results of EDS.

Implementation of Quality Fulfillment Planning: TPMPD's commitment to quality fulfillment has been prepared with activities to implement education quality fulfillment planning. The activity did not run optimally considering that the database is in the OPS, where the OPS does not handle only one team but many teams, so the OPS is overwhelmed with its responsibilities. Furthermore, make the ops burden heavy. The result is that the fulfillment of quality is less than optimal. Evaluation Monitoring: Internal quality evaluation monitoring is carried out to ensure continuous quality improvement. Based on the document observations, the school's internal evaluation monitoring schedule is at least once a semester. Based on the research findings, this internal monitoring and evaluation activity has not been carried out optimally due to the limited availability and ability of the internal audit team. As a result of the large number of teams formed by schools, many tasks are duplicated. Determination of B are Quality Standards: At this stage, the school sets new quality standards as a benchmark for the following year's program. The new quality may be a standard above the SNP if, based on the quality audit results, the previous year's achievements have met the SNP or even exceeded the SNP. In addition, at this stage, schools also need to establish new strategies for quality fulfillment at standards that obtain moderate and insufficient grades. The establishment of new quality standards beyond the SNP will be an extra capital for schools to obtain the best

accreditation status. Similarly, establishing a new strategy for the fulfillment of quality that has not met the SNP is a curative action for schools to continuously strive to improve themselves and improve their quality. This will maintain the consistency of improving the quality achievement of each SNP standard from year to year until the school/islamic school accreditation assessment period arrives.

Based on the quality report card, elementary schools in Madiun City are achieving SNP because the achievements in the previous year were towards (M4). The result of the Internal Quality Assurance System is that there is an improvement in the quality of education at the school level from time to time-based on the indicators set related to quality culture, namely: (1) Schools implement SPMI, so not all criteria have been met, meaning that there are still schools that have not implemented the quality assurance cycle independently, have a quality assurance team in schools, have not reached SNP; (2) The school has some superiority, which school-based management has not achieved; (3) as a learning resource center for surrounding schools, it has not been achieved, especially many of the schools that are fostered. The following is an analysis of the factors inhibiting school management in realizing a quality culture: (1) The results of the analysis of the low value achievement of implementing aspects of the curriculum that are not in accordance with the provisions, (2) The lowest achievement in school culture management in involving principals, teachers, OPS, staff, committees and other stakeholders; (3) Currently, many teams are formed within the school and work partially, causing the enormous workload of the school and the school management process to overlap, ineffective and inefficient, (4) Related to the role of implementing the role of TPMPS in realizing a quality culture is still less than optimal, because TPMPS members are also members of other teams who work partially, so that the focus on TPMPS becomes divided, (5) When the school has obtained a quality report card, a valid quality report card is carried out, some schools submit it to the OPS, this makes the task of the OPS heavy The result of meeting the quality is less than optimal, (6) Low competence in analyzing quality data and the root of the problem, (7) The school has implemented a quality fulfillment plan that is not in accordance with the previously prepared plan and the schedule prepared. (8) Monitoring the internal evaluation is not carried out optimally, (9) Supervision here tends to be administrative, so it is said that the implementation of learning supervision is less than optimal. (10) Primary Schools in Madiun City have not yet reached SNP, and (11) Schools are less than optimal in involving the community in building partnerships.

The following is informed of the analysis results of factors supporting school management in realizing a quality culture. (1) Schools are aware of the content of KTSP, (2) All schools in the area of the Madiun City Education Office form TPMPS. (3) Schools are committed to implementing SPMI in realizing a quality culture. (4) Schools conduct EDS using quality mapping instruments (quality report cards) and conduct quality data analysis and root causes. (5) The school has implemented school-based management. (6) The school has a complete document of school-based management and SPMI, and (7) The school can increase SNP scores each year. They are managing learning facilities and infrastructure. (8) The school has a management information system to support education administration. (9) All teachers and education personnel have the qualifications following the provisions. As previously explained, to reduce the massive burden on schools, the integration of existing teams in schools is carried out various quality improvement efforts and to empower TPMPS and other stakeholders using the whole school development approach, which is a comprehensive school development approach that involves all school residents (education leaders, principals, teachers, staff, and parents in order to achieve commonality. Vision and mission to realize a quality culture that is effective and efficient. Meanwhile, Karen Taylor, a Senior Education Adviser (Whole School and district Development) at the Managing Contractor Program Management - Australia Indonesia Basic Education Program (MCPM AIBEP), asked what is meant by the Whole School Development Approach: In simple terms, Whole School Development is a mechanism used to improve and uplift schools' academic, infrastructural, social, and security environments. WSD aims primarily to ensure that schools have the necessary resources to support an environment conducive to excellence in teaching and learning in every school the Adopt-a-School Foundation works in.

In simple terms, the whole school development approach is used to improve and elevate schools' academic, infrastructure, social, and environmental security fields. WSD aims primarily to ensure that schools have the necessary resources to support an environment conducive to excellence in each school's teaching and learning process. The whole school development approach aims to increase learning opportunities for children through increasing the capacity of essential people in schools/islamic schools, the family, and the community. The whole school development approach refers to improving the quality of School-Based Management (SBM) and focuses on planning and developing educational units according to national education standards (SNP) The concept of school-based management has become part of government policy. Therefore, Thomas L. Wheeler argues that achieving practical change

goals requires clarity of objectives, both those concerning processes and developments by involving internal and external aspects to be taken into consideration. Individuals, principals, teachers, employees, and the condition of the school itself are dotted with goals, mastery of skills, attitudes, self-concept, and habits of results and processes. Agents of change are teachers and principals, while the objects of change are institutions, curricula, learning, and the like.

Figure 3. Proposed School Management Model in Realizing a Quality culture

Source: Modified model La Ode Rahmat Putra Rustaman ST

D. Conclusion

On the results of research on school management analysis in realizing culture in elementary schools in Madiun City, it can be concluded as follows: (1) School management in Madiun City Elementary Schools has met the criteria of quality culture, namely implementing SPMI, having various advantages, and becoming a learning resource for surrounding schools. The criteria for implementing SPMI have not been achieved because elementary schools in Madiun City have not reached SNP, school management has not been running according to standards and not all of them have become learning resources for surrounding schools, so that it can be informed that school management is not optimal, so that the quality culture has not been realized in accordance with government expectations; (2) Success factors, there are several factors that support the success of school management in realizing a quality culture, namely the school is committed to implementing SPMI towards a quality cultured school in accordance with applicable regulations, supported by educators and education personnel who have qualifications according to the provisions, the existence of a management information system and availability of special officers; (3) The inhibiting factor is the low achievement value of the implementation of curriculum aspects that are not in accordance with the provisions because the application of local content curriculum aspects and the regulation of learning load based on the form of material deepening is still low and the implementation of the learning and assessment process is not in accordance with the provisions. c. school management model to make school management more effective requires maximum stakeholder involvement through

the implementation of the learning and assessment process is not following the provisions. The school management model to make school management more effective requires maximum stakeholder involvement through a Whole school development approach.

E. References

- Abdul Hadi (2018). *Konsep Manajemen Mutu dalam Pendidikan Universitas Nurul Jadid Paiton Probolinggo*. Jurnal Idaarah, Vol. II, No. 2, Desember 2018.
- Abdulloh Hadziq (2016). *Implementasi Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah (School Based Management) Dalam Mewujudkan Sekolah Efektif (Studi Kasus Di MTs NU Sabilul Muttaqin Jepang Mejobo Kudus)*. Jurnal QUALITY Vol. 4, No. 2, 2016: 351-371 p-ISSN: 2355-0333, e-ISSN: 2502-8324.
- Ahmad, Dzaujak. "Penunjuk Peningkatan Mutu pendidikan di sekolah Dasar." Jakarta: Depdikbud, 1996.
- Ahmad Darmadji (2015). *Pengembangan Madrasah Berbasis Manajemen Mutu Total Untuk Meningkatkan Moral Bangsa*. Jurnal Pendidikan Islam El Tarbawy. ISSN: 1979998-5 [Halaman 1 - 18] DOI: http://dx.doi.org/10.20885/El_Tarbawi.vol8.iss1.art1.
- Amir (2019) *Membangun Budaya Mutu Pada Lembaga Pendidikan Islam Menuju Madrasah Unggul*. Institut Agama Islam Negeri, Jember, Indonesia AITanzim: Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Islam E-ISSN: 2549-5720 P-ISSN: 2549-3663 Vol. 03 No. 02 (2019) : 1-12
- Anang Dwi Putransu Aspranawa (2015). *Memahami Quality Assurance Menjadikan Budaya Mutu Perguruan Tinggi Universitas Islam Blitar*, Blitar AN-NISBAH, Vol. 01, No. 02, April 2015- 111
- Asrohah, Hanun. "Manajemen Mutu Pendidikan." Surabaya: UIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya, 2014.
- Ascaro, Jerome S. "Quality in Education: An Implementation Handbook" (alihbahasa: Yosali Iriantara, "Pendidikan Berbasis Mutu: Prinsip-Prinsip Perumusan dan Tata Langkah Penerapan." Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar, 2007.
- Kaisya Azzahra Kadar Sarifan Dan Rasto (2017) *Keterampilan Manajerial Kepala Sekolah Dan Budaya Mutu Sebagai Determinan Kinerja Guru (Principal's Managerial Skills And Quality Culture As Determinants Of Teacher Performance)* Jurnal Pendidikan Manajemen Perkantoran Vol. 2 No. 2, Juli 2017, Hal. 137-147
- Barbara S. Hawley (2019), *How Principals Enact Instructional Leadership In K-5 Urban Schools*. Dissertation. Kent State University College. Benjamin Kutsyuruba (2017). *Creating Supportive School Cultures for Beginning Teachers: Mitigating the Cultural Contextual Factors*. Article in International Journal of Educational Organization and Leadership · May 2017 DOI: 10.18848/2329-1656/CGP/v24i02/1-18.

- Budimansyah, Dasim. "Peningkatan Mutu Pendidikan Melalui Penguatan Partisipasi Masyarakat." *Educationist*, 2, 2008.
- Bugin, Burhan. "Analisis Data Penelitian Kualitatif." Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada, 2003.
- Depdiknas. "Manajemen Peningkatan Mutu Berbasis Sekolah." Jakarta: Depdiknas. 2004.
- Deming, W. Edwards. "Out of the Crisis." Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1986, dalam Anonim, "Manajemen Mutu Pendidikan" <http://guruidaman.blogspot.com>.
- Dian Sari (2019). Analisis Inovasi Pelayanan Publik "KELAS PERAHU" Kabupaten Pangkajene dan Kepulauan. *Jurnal SAP Vol. 3 No.3 April 2019* p-ISSN: 2527-967X e-ISSN: 2549-2845
- Dirjed Pendidikan Dasar dan Menengah. 2017. Indikator Mutu dalam Budaya mutu Pendidikan Dasar dan Menengah. Dirjend Dikdasmen: Jakarta.
- Dirjed Pendidikan Dasar dan Menengah. 2017. Petunjuk Pelaksanaan Budaya mutu Pendidikan Oleh Satuan Pendidikan. Dirjend Dikdasmen: Jakarta. Direktorat Jenderal Pendidikan Dasar dan Menengah
- Dit. PSMA Ditjen. Pendidikan Dasar dan Menengah. 2017. Implementasi Pengembangan Kecakapan Abad 21 Dalam Perencanaan Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran (RPP).
- Dit. PSMA Ditjen. Pendidikan Dasar dan Menengah: Jakarta. Dragana Glušac, et al (2015) Study Of Impact Of School Culture On The Teaching And Learning Process In Serbia Based On School Evaluation. *Jurnal UDK - 373.31(497.11) 37.014:006* DOI: 10.5937/nasvas1502255G HB год. LXIV 2.2015.
- Fattah, Nanang. "Landasan Manajemen Pendidikan." Bandung: Remaja Rosda Karya, 1996.
- Gaspersz, Vincent. "Total Quality Management." Jakarta: Gramedia PustakaUtama, 2001.
- Hamdan Husein Batubara (2017) Implementasi Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah Di SDN Sungai Miai 5 Dan SDN Surgi Mufti 4 Di Banjarmasin. Article In *ALULUM Jurnal Ilmu Sosial Dan Humaniora*. April 2018 DOI: 10.31602/Alsh.V3i2.1196AL-Ulum: Jurnal Ilmu Sosial Dan Humaniora ISSN: 2476-9576 Volume 3 Noor 2, Oktober 2017.
- Hendrikus Midun (2017). Membangun Budaya Mutu Dan Unggul Di Sekolah. Universitas Negeri Malang. *Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Kebudayaan Missio*, Volume 9, Nomor 1, Januari 2017, Hlm. 50-59.
- Hendro Widodo (2019) Revitalisasi Sekolah Berbasis Budaya Mutu. Universitas Ahmad Dahlan Yogyakarta, Indonesia *Jurnal Administrasi Pendidikan* 26 (1) (2019) 57-71 ISSN: P.1412-8152 E.2580-1007 |
- Instruksi Presiden Nomor 4 Tahun 1995 tentang Gerakan Nasional Memasyarakatkan dan Membudayakan Kewirausahaan.
- Khadiyanto, Parfi. "Partisipasi Masyarakat dalam Pembangunan Unit Sekolah Baru." Penerbit: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro Semarang, (2007).

- Kemendikbud. “Panduan Pelaksanaan Pemetaan Mutu Pendidikan Tahun 2013.” Jakarta: Badan Pengembangan SDM dan Penjaminan Mutu Pendidikan Kemendikbud, 2013.
- Moh.Zaini (2016). Manajemen Peningkatan Mutu Berbasis Madrasah.Desertasi Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang.
- Muhamad Khoirul Umam (2020). Dinamisasi Manajemen Mutu Persfektif Pendidikan Islam. Jurnal Al-Hikmah Vol 8 Maret 2020| 61~74.
- Małgorzata Dzimi (2018) Trust-Based Quality Culture Conceptual Model for Higher Education Institutions, University of Social Sciences, 9 Sienkiewicza Street, 90-113 Łód’z, Polandia Sustainability 2018, 10, 2599; doi:10.3390/su10082599.
- Nasrul Amin,dkk (2018)Membangun Budaya Mutu yang Unggul Dalam Organisasi lembaga Pendidikan Islam. Universitas Nurul JadidPaiton Probolinggo Jawa Timur Jurnal Al TanzimVolume 2 Nomor 1 2018ISSN: 2549-3663
- Nurhayati, dkk (2018). The Principal’s Leadership Strategy in Improving Quality: A Study at Aron State Elementary School Pidie Aceh Indonesia. Advances in Sosial Science, Education and Humanities Research, volume 269.
- Nurmaini MY(2019).Meraih Mutu Sekolah Melalui Data Mutu: Suatu Tinjauan. Jurnal Ilmiah Universitas Batanghari Jambi, 19(2): 347-352 DOI 10.33087/jiubj.v19i2.677 ISSN 1411-8939 (Online) | ISSN 2549-4236 (Print)
- Rais Hidayat, dkk (2018) Optimalisasi Budaya Mutu Sekolah Untuk meningkatkan Komitmen Guru. Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Vol.6, No.2, Juli 2018 PISSN 2302-0296 E-ISSN 2614-3313.
- Reckson Kamusoko& Raphael Jingura (2019) A competency framework for internal quality assurance in higher education. Article in International Journal of Management in Education· January 2019 DOI: 10.1504/IJMIE.2019.10018030
- Riyanta,Teguh (2016) Mengembangkan Budaya Mutu Sekolah Melalui Kepemimpinan Transformasional. Jurnal manajemen pendidikan Vol. 12, No. 2, Oktober 2016.
- Rais Hidayat,Dkk (2018) Optimalisasi Budaya Mutu Sekolah Untuk Peningkatkan Komitmen Guru. Jurnal Manajemen Pendidikan Vol.6, No.2, Juli 2018 PISSN 2302-0296 E-ISSN 2614-3313.
- Robi Cahyadi Kurniawan (2016) Tantangan Kualitas Pelayanan Publik Pada Pemerintah Daerah. Jurnal Ilmiah Administrasi Publik dan Pembangunan, Vol. 7 No. 1, Januari-Juni 2016 ISSN: 2087
- Senggo dan Abdul Kadir (2016) Budaya Organisasi Dalam Pelayanan Publik (Studi Pada Badan Penyelenggara Pelayanan Perizinan Kota Kendari) eJournal - Publica, PPS AP-UHO, ISSN: 2502-5589 Edisi Januari 2016, Volume I No 1
- Siti Aminah & Ari Dwi Widodo (2019), Membangun Budaya Mutu Di Madrasah Unggul (Studi Kasus di MAN 1 Jember Dan MA).
- Undang-Undang Nomor 20 Tahun 2003 tentang Sistem Pendidikan Nasional.